

LA TUTORÍA ACADÉMICA Y LA INVESTIGACIÓN HISTÓRICA EN LA ESCUELA DE CIENCIAS SOCIALES DE LA UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE CHIMBORAZO (ECUADOR).

INTEGRAL TUTORING AND HISTORICAL RESEARCH IN THE SCHOOL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES OF THE NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF CHIMBORAZO (ECUADOR).

Authors:

Roque Herrera, Y.⁽¹⁾; Alonso–García, S.⁽²⁾; Valdivia-Moral, P.⁽³⁾

Institution:

⁽¹⁾ Universidad Nacional de Chimborazo (Ecuador), yosbroque@hotmail.com

⁽²⁾ Universidad Nacional de Educación (Ecuador),
santiago.alonso@unae.edu.ec

⁽³⁾ Consejería de Educación y Ciencia. Junta de Andalucía,
pedro.valdivia@dempc.uhu.es

Resumen:

Se realizó una investigación aplicada de tipo descriptiva, con el propósito de diagnosticar el estado de la investigación histórica en el contexto educativo de la Facultad de Ciencias de la Educación, Humanas y Tecnologías en la UNACH. Se empleó la estadística descriptiva para el análisis de los datos. Los principales resultados obtenidos fueron: La Carrera de Ciencias Sociales mantiene un alto nivel de ingreso a la misma, y la mayoría de sus estudiantes manifiestan tener interés por el estudio de la Historia; Los niveles de investigación histórica en el universo estudiado es insuficiente, siendo el tema de historia local el más investigado por ellos, encontrando en la biblioteca de la facultad tres de ellas con una metodología investigativa que muestra

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insuficiencias; Los estudiantes declaran que la mayoría de las veces han investigado temas históricos como parte de tareas docentes encargadas por sus profesores, más casi siempre en forma de revisiones bibliográficas; Profesores y estudiantes de la población coinciden en que el acceso a fuentes de información documentales primarias es muy difícil, utilizando mayormente los recursos disponibles del internet; Predominaron los miembros de la población que manifiestan necesitar capacitación sobre metodología para la investigación histórica para los Tutores de Educación Superior (Alonso, S.; Palomares, A., 2013).

Abstract:

With the aim of diagnosing the state of the Historical Research in the educational context of the Faculty of Sciences of Education, Humanities and Technology at the UNACH an applied research of the descriptive type was developed. For the analysis of data, Descriptive statistics was applied. The main obtained results were: The School of Social Sciences keeps a high level of admission, and most of its students report to be interested in the study of History. The levels of Historical Research in the universe studied is insufficient, the theme of local history is the most investigated by the students, at the faculty library three of those studies were found with a research methodology that shows insufficiencies. The students report that most of the times, they have researched historical topics as part of their school tasks assigned by their teachers, mostly as literature reviews. Professor and students of the population coincide that access to the primary document sources of information is very difficult; they use mostly the resources available on the Internet. The members of the population who say the Tutors of Higher Education need training on methodology for historical research were the predominated ones. (Alonso, S.; Palomares, A., 2013).

Key Words:

Historical Research, education, integral tutoring, higher education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Historical research, from our perspective, can make a critical analysis of the past and rethink the history constantly, it observes every source not considered or considered in the existing theories to confirm, enrich or refute them. Universities have a social and an academic function of seeking the truth constantly and a historical truth is essential to understand who we are and where we are going.

History is one of the most important branches of human knowledge, and it is the fundamental base of the culture of all professionals, no matter what their specialty is. It is also an essential source for the ideological training of the citizens of each country, so it is not possible to conceive a member of a social community without precise knowledge of their history. This undoubtedly will allow them to love their roots, consciously understand the present and help them to shape the future of their country and humanity. (Garcia, 2010)

There is one aspect which is necessary to mention because of its importance for the regional and local history, and it is the close relationship between them and the national or general History; if it is true that to know about the history of a nation it is necessary to study and deepen regional particularities and the history of localities, in turn, when we face the study of a region, area or city, we have to take into account that it is part of the national context, which influences their behavior; it means, it is not isolated, and it is necessary to take into account the relationship between the singular and the general aspects, between the whole and its parts.

"[...] what is general must be sought and found (or not found) through the particular and vice versa. Without this cross-fertilization, neither the general history of a society is as it is; neither the provincial and local history can aspire to exceed the limits of what is episodic, it exhausts in itself." (Roque, 2013)

The fundamental method of Historical Research is the analytic-synthetic. It is essential in the study of historical issues to analyze the events decomposing them in its entirety to know their economic, social, political, religious or ethnographic possible roots, and based on this analysis to carry out

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synthesis to reconstruct and explain the historical fact. (Ali Fernandez Gonzalez, Rodriguez & De Zayas, 2007)

The analytical method is heuristic, word comes from the Greek term *heurisko*, it means, *I seek, discover*, and that is the method used to find what is new, what is unknown. In History, it would be the handling of written and oral sources mainly, but for the study of Prehistory, it would be necessary to resort to other auxiliary sciences, which will be discussed later. (Ali et al., 2007).

The synthesis method is hermeneutics, from the Greek word *hermeneuo*, which means *I explain*, that is the art and theory of interpretation, which aims to clarify the meaning of the text based on their objective bases (grammatical meanings of words and their variations historically conditioned) and subjective (authors' purposes). (Ali et al., 2007).

Historical research is deductive-inductive too. Deduction, from the Latin word *deductio*, it means *to determine consequences from a principle, proposal or course*, it is used to name the method of reasoning leading to the conclusion from general to particular. (Ali et al., 2007).

Induction comes from the Latin term *inductio*, it means *move one, to persuade, incite*, it names the method of reasoning which ensures the possibility of moving from the singular facts to general propositions, or from what is particular to what is general. Although the general History of a country is not just the sum of its local stories, it is very important to know the particular facts to reach the most real conclusions on the results of Historical Research. (Ali et al., 2007).

Thus, the method of historical research must go from the general to the particular scope, but it must be completed from the particular to the general one. Among the main submethods of Historical Research are the Chronological, Geographical and Ethnographic method. (Ali et al., 2007) The Chronologic method is the most important. Chronology name comes from the Greek Cronos, who is the God of Time, so the knowledge of the development of events in successive order of dates is essential for all Historical Research. Since this research, it is extremely easy the historical interpretation. (Ali et al., 2007).

The Geographical sub method is which tries events in order of people. The history of a country or region cannot be written if there is not finished knowledge of its geography. (Ali et al., 2007).

Finally, the Ethnographic sub method that relates historical facts by races, nationalities, religions, and other cultural events.

The sources for History growing are first writings or documents that are written sources that are the most important. Many authors agree on the idea that History begins with writing.

Among the most common ways of describing History are found chronic, which exposes what happened in a government or region limited by an active or passive observer of the events that were narrated. The ephemeris in that History is narrated by days. The memoirs, in which historical facts are told by someone who acted somehow in certain events. (Ali et al., 2007).

The greatest danger to History is given today by the resurrection of the historic pseudo- materialism as a form of intellectual opportunism that can easily confuse the masses, especially the new generations. Partial truths or half-lies twist facts and distort the importance of certain personalities for the benefit of social class with political power or other power sectors. In this globalized world, where important means of disseminating information are mostly in the hands and to the service of the powerful people, it is common that History is told for their own benefit. (Martinez, 2013).

The resources to go back and document a particular place are almost limitless. The documentation may be a recognition site, oral histories, and records created by government offices, businesses, institutions, individuals and organizations. Recognition of land, census records made, city directories, water department records, correspondence, photos, brochures goods companies, all provide valuable information about changes in the neighborhood. Researchers will need to consult some of those resources to collect all the information. (Ali et al., 2007).

Given this background, it is necessary people and professionals linked to the academy-research, tutors HET (higher education tutors), trained and convinced to overcome the traits that shape us as beings of this century (uncertainty, Roque Herrera, Y.; Alonso–García, S.; Valdivia-Moral, P. (2015). La tutoría académica 28 y la investigación histórica en la escuela de ciencias sociales de la Universidad Nacional De Chimborazo (ECUADOR). *Trances*, 8(1):23-46.

complexity and antagonism) and educational processes (live, critic, transformer, caring, creative) that can provide various way of approach (Alonso, S .; Palomares, A., 2013).

These HET, by their guiding work, must constitute the essence of humans that has to deploy socially and make sense again to all, in this world of social and evolutionary stress. (Alonso, S .; Palomares, A., 2013).

Given the theoretical framework in which we have contextualized this investigation, then we proceed to the methodological approach.

2. SCIENTIFIC PROBLEM.

What is the situation of Historical Research in the educational context of the Faculty of Sciences of Education, Humanities and Technology at the UNACH?

3. OBJECTIVE.

1. To determine the status of Historical Research from the point of view of students and teachers in the educational context of the Faculty of Sciences of Education, Humanities and Technology at the UNACH.
2. To propose future research and innovation.

4. POPULATION AND SAMPLE.

The project was developed with the total population constituted by all investigations of historical type recorded and filed, teachers and students of the school, in the Faculty of Sciences of Education, Humanities and Technology at the UNACH besides teachers and students of the School of Social Sciences.

5. METHODS AND INSTRUMENTS.

Descriptive applied research was performed by triangulating instruments, in order to diagnose the state of Historical Research in the educational context at the Faculty of Sciences of Education, Humanities and Technology at the UNACH.

Theoretical methods

- Analytical synthetic method.

- Historic logical method.

Instruments

- Document review uuide.
- Semi-structured interview guide
- Questionnaire.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The analysis of the results of the instruments for carrying out an action plan for promoting Historical Research in the context studied permitted to establish an accurate diagnosis on the characteristics of the environment in which it was developed, it seeks to responds to the real needs and potential.

The study focused on the School of Social Sciences for its obvious relationship to this field of research: Historical Research. This school was, at the time of the investigation, which had the largest enrollment of students in the Faculty of Sciences of Education, Humanities and Technology with 152 students enrolled. Students mentioned that they have chosen the School of Social Sciences, to understand better the society through its theoretical and practical study and its evolution over time; and thus contribute by diagnosing and solving their problems, to help in the improvement of quality of life of a community or society in general.

Table 1. Level of welcome expressed by the sample on the study of history

VERY MUCH	MUCH	LITTLE	TOTAL
87	40	25	152
57,24%	26,32%	16,45%	100,00%

Source: authors

In line with the views of the sample analyzed above, over 80% of students surveyed said that they like very much or much the study of History; this is the essential aspect in the motivation for the study and an important step to achieve significant learning.

Pilar Benejam poses, to the student wishes to make an effort to accept the doubts that generates new knowledge and operating mechanisms of learning, requires a lot of motivation. If the motivation is efficient and appropriate, they will confront what they know with the new learning, generate a conflict to be resolved in a process of accommodation and assimilation that allows the incorporation of a new concept to supplement a previous one that establishes new relationships or arrangements among concepts or correct or change a wrong one. (Casal, 2011)

Table 2. Performance of Historical Research before applying the instrument by students in the sample

	Semesters							total	%
	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th	4 th year		
YES	11	12	5	0	4	4	10	46	30,26
NO	21	20	14	19	14	7	11	106	69,73

Source: authors

69.73% of the students surveyed said they have done Historical Research prior to application of the instrument. Most of the students mentioned that the

researches were made in the as of literature reviews, without using the various methods used for Historical Research.

The quality of higher education is associated with the practice of research. Now when we talk about research in this context referred not only to do research but also it refers to the search and generation of knowledge, the experience of high-level research, rather than the mere fact of linking research products to teaching practices. (Zorrilla, 2011)

The research topics, which were dealt by the students surveyed, suggest a preference for the topics of local history, but also coincidence with the subjects of the curriculum was observed; the last one showed relation with the fact that most investigations were oriented as assessment tasks on different topics received in class. It is suggested that teachers redirect their teaching and methodological work towards the encouragement of scientific curiosity and critical questioning of society as fundamental to complement the training of students via.

Similarly, Sell (1996), referring to formative research, he said, the formative research can focus on the strengths and weaknesses of a program or course in search of a diagnostic about what can be changed in these ones to improve, and to check if those changes actually produce improvements.

It was observed that over 90% of the subjects in which Historical Research was originated was proper of this science. The teaching of any science is inevitably marked by its historical development in different political, social and natural environments; the tendency to despise the role of History is an attack on the quality of future graduates of any branch of science or profession. (Sanfeliú, 2012)

Table 3. Sources of information used for Historical Research experiences for students in the sample.

SOURCES	1st wee k	2n d we ek	3rd we ek	4th we ek	5th we ek	6th wee k	4th yea r	tota l
HISTORY BOOK	3	4	--	--	1	2	1	11
ARTICLES FROM INTERNET	3	8	2	--	--	2	--	15
MUSEUM PIECES	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	1
FOOTAGE	--	2	--	--	--	--	1	3

Source: authors

The prevalence of Internet use and the history books confirms that most of the research has the features of literature review; footage is the least used (Table 3). Everything leads to a clear need to strengthen the rigorous Historical Research that allows us to know an area of history more deeply, from a critical perspective that searches the sources of information that might provide new data reliably. This is not an easy task, as described in her article Tiana Ferrer "The project manes and Historical Research on textbooks (s. XIX and XX)", but it is a priority, and the quality of the result will depend largely on Historical Research. (Tiana Ferrer, 2000)

Table 4. Level of difficulty in accessing information sources for Historical Research.

SCALE	Semesters						4 th	TOTAL
	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th	year	
high	2	2	0	0	2	1	3	10
medium	8	8	5	0	2	3	3	29
low	1	1	4	0	0	0	3	9
TOTAL	11	11	9	0	4	4	9	48

Source: authors

The degree of difficulty in accessing these sources, even though restricted sources were not used (files, personalities, etc.) ranged from high and medium according to the experience of the sample (Table 4). The location, selection and proper use of information sources is an obligatory task in Historical Research; Tiana Ferrer saying: "Anyone who tried to approach rigorously in this field of study verified the enormous difficulties, often encountering the researcher forced to use partial and indirect sources, if he does not make a real work of school archeology. The identification and location of appropriate fonts often becomes a priority task, which consumes a lot of energy. This does not mean, however, that some valuable and relatively accessible information resources do not exist to rebuild the internal history ... "(Tiana Ferrer, 2000)

151 students were involved in the study population, 141 of them attached great importance to Historical Research in their professional training, but 136 which represent the 89.47% need extra training and presence of activities to develop this skill and therefore 138 students expressed interest in participating in activities that would offer improvement in the future.

The scientific methodological rigor of Historical Research developed in the studied context was determined through the analysis of the final reports deposited in the library of the Faculty of Sciences of Education, Humanities and Technology at the UNACH. From 11 written works shortlisted, three were finally recognized as essentially Historical Research and only based on them this target was met.

Table 5. Methodological Scientific rigor demonstrated in the research reports filed in the university library and they are classified as historical.

Aspects evaluated	Excellent		Very good		good		Regular		bad	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Main Topic	--	--	2	66.67	1	33.33	--	--	--	--
Justification	1	33.33	1	33.33	1	33.33	--	--	--	--
Objectives	--	--	1	33.33	2	66.67	--	--	--	--
Methodology	--	--	--	--	--	--	3	100	--	--
Results and discussion	--	--	--	--	1	33.33	2	66.67	--	--
Conclusions	--	--	--	--	1	33.33	2	66.67	--	--
Bibliographic References	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3	100
Annexes	--	--	--	--	--	--	3	100	--	--

Source: authors.

It was observed a shortage of research on History and methodological problems were prevalent founded in it. Shortcomings are denoted in drafting and

realization of results. Research on the thought of Monsignor Proaño was the best qualified, but with their own inadequacies of unpreparedness for conducting such research.

Hugo Klappenbach, in his article entitled "About the Research Methodology in the History of Psychology", raises the need to implement workshops methodological improvement if it is required to conduct Historical Research with a critical purpose that really contribute to science and society in general. (Klappenbach, 2014).

An interview was performed to the teachers to triangulate results from other instruments and sources, as well as to get their criteria. All teachers interviewed had third and fourth degree in sciences related directly with History, except one of them; this was a very suitable situation for the development of Historical Research activities, even contradictory regarding the results shown in number, scientific rigor and type of research that has been found in the context studied.

In the sample studied of teachers, there was predominance of teachers with less than 5 years of experience in higher education; this was a factor, which could influence the low scientific productivity in terms of Historical Research, for little or no experience in higher education.

Any science professionals should be related to the past of that science and humanity in general, they try to train their students in the exaltation of the importance of this knowledge. The orientation of activities that allow them to explore in the past allow students a better understanding of what they have studied about the insertion in the social context of their science. (Klappenbach, 2014).

In the sample of teachers studied, there was a predominance of professionals that guide Historical Research activities, although most teachers said they have focused only on literature reviews; which coincided with the issues raised by the students surveyed.

All the respondents said they used historical themes in its class, for a better understanding of the content, although it should be noted that the School of

Social Sciences has a curriculum that depends essentially of knowledge of History to reach the profile of graduate established.

Thus, It is possible to say that a teaching strategy from a historical point of view, is the path or route that teachers should employ to make learning more effective in students, through actions to build knowledge in the school environment and interaction with communities.

Contemporary Higher Education's mission is to "train highly qualified professionals to act as responsible citizens, competent and committed to social development" (UNESCO, 1998), a mission that cannot be comply from the principles of traditional teaching that focuses on the teacher as a transmitter of knowledge and values that are played by students in an uncritically and decontextualized way in relation to the professional practice. (Gonzalez, 2004).

The teachers interviewed agreed with the students in the degree of difficulty of access to primary sources of information for Historical Research, as well as internet use and books in libraries as sources most commonly used.

Respondents agree that Historical Research is insufficient, they felt that it was not given importance to this area of knowledge, coupled with the lack of knowledge on ways to perform this type of research, requiring incentives through training on handling of sources, methods and techniques and appropriate tools.

In the practice of the knowledge of society, research and teaching is derived. The first one takes place on structured hypothesis that require standing work through a complex portfolio of methodological tools and shared results identified with the consensus. This true implies an exchange of arguments between suppliers and recipients using well-established competences, so that a vision of complementarity for the research is applied, this is teaching through didactics, teaching what is known to who knows less, but according that student becomes an expert, he becomes a member supporting the diatribe that improves his competence, and introduced into the dialectic of research, it means, in the game of scientific knowledge who uses the respective languages or target languages of a segment of knowledge legitimizing its heuristic competition beyond the positivism and whose language is philosophical.

Historical research power their professional development to let the learning of past events in order to understand the present and envision the future. The main axes of history are time and space, as the historical facts once found in time must be located in the place of occurrence and registered geographically. Historical knowledge helps us to understand that humans have always organized themselves into groups, tribes, people and nations in search of solidarity and identity. It emphasizes the social nature of human beings and invites us to know the languages, ethnic traits, territory, family relations and political organization.

Considering the features found proceeded to propose a program of activities to promote Historical Research in the School of Social Sciences at UNACH; with objectives for each activity:

1. To increase the activity of vocational guidance and promotion of the school that is studied.
2. To raise the motivation and training of teachers and students to develop Historical Research.
3. To promote the comprehensive analysis of historical facts by the teacher during teaching, from a contextual and multi-disciplinary perspective, emphasizing the critical and reflective thinking in students.
4. To increase the scientific rigor and the amount of Historical Research in the field studied.
5. To create environments of historical knowledge management for teachers and students.
6. To locate and manage access to historical information to facilitate the work of researchers.
7. To socialize standards and experiences between tutors and courts of thesis in the field of Historical Research.

Table 6. Program to promote Historical Research in the School of Social Sciences at UNACH

Executors	Activity	Time	Means
Direction of the School	Methodological guidelines and workshops for teachers about teaching methods in teaching and research of historical themes.	2 hours.	Printed documents.
Teachers of the School Committee.	Discussion with students of leveling who aspired to enter to the School of Social Sciences.	2 hours.	Board, projector, computer.
Teachers of the School Committee.	Discussion with high school students of last level to promote the School of Social Sciences, encouraging them to choose it.	2 hours.	Board, projector, computer.
Direction of the school	Controls to teaching activities about historical themes.	2 hours.	Guide.
Project team.	To advice and guidance to teachers of the school on possible topics for Historical Research and during the investigative processes of this type.	1 hour.	Printed documents.

Direction of the school with the members of the project	Development of workshops, seminars and scientific conferences on historical themes.	6 hours	Auditorium, theater faculty, classrooms for teaching and technological resources.
Members of the project team and other teachers of the school.	To create historical documentation centers in their custody and establish agreements among them for access to information.	4 hours.	Transportation and printed promotional materials.
Members of the project team.	To design and conduct training activities for teachers and students about methodology for Historical Research.	At least 40 hours	Classrooms and an auditorium with teaching and technological resources.
Direction of School with members of the project.	Workshops discussing about standards and experiences between tutors and courts of thesis in the field of Historical Research.	2 hours.	Classrooms with teaching and technologic resources.

Methodological indications of the program.

The activities are carried out gradually, it is necessary to start with the activities of motivation to conclude with those related to scientific productivity in the area of History. Awareness begin by members of the faculty and then they work with students. The training research work from the classroom will be promoted

without forcing students to participate when activities are not within their curricular training.

Activities 2 and 3 will be previously planned with the different academic units. The discussion should be as a workshop, using participatory techniques with relevant teaching aids. For them, a simple tool will be applied to assess the situation with regard to knowledge about History and the importance attached to its knowledge.

The observation on historical teaching activities will take place using a guide to assessing the teaching and at the same time it feedback to the teacher that taught it. (Program Activity 4)

The advice to teachers who work in Historical Research will be provided by teachers with more experience in this area, (activity 5) but preferably it should be done after the first training sessions that are offered to avoid large theoretical and methodological differences.

To fulfill activity 6, the spaces of knowledge management created for teachers should not distinguish specialty, level of education or other characteristic that discriminates those who wish to participate. All activities in this regard should be accredited depending on the level at which it takes place and relevance. The first activities must be workshops for discussion and sharing of experiences then, they transcend to more complex forms according to the increase in the productivity in Historical Research related to its scientific rigor and quantity.

The lifting of the centers or institutions with historical information of relevance and reliability will be done considering libraries, archives, associations, people who witnessed historical events, etc. agreements with the relevant authorities or people will be made to flow the future research work. (Activity 7)

Before the design of the improvement programs on Historical Research, a survey of learning needs should be carried out. (Activity 8) The training will be designed giving priority to active teaching methods, with an emphasis on practical activities. Teachers will be selected according to the thematic and research experience in History, determined by productivity.

Activity 9 aims to teachers who act as courts or guardians of theses with strong component of Historical Research to share their experiences, concerns and questions to arrive at best practices in this important work.

Allow activities designed to reverse the current situation in terms of Historical Research in the context studied, in the judgment of experts who evaluated the proposal designed.

7. CONCLUSIONS

- The School of Social Sciences showed a high level of income to it, and most students have expressed interest in the study of History.
- The levels of scientific productivity in terms of Historical Research on students and teachers of the universe studied was insufficient, being the subject of the most researched local history for them, although the use of the scientific method showed significant weaknesses.
- Students stated that most of the time they have investigated historical subjects as part of their teaching tasks assigned by their teachers, but almost always in the form of literature reviews.
- Teachers and students of the population agreed that access to primary sources of documentary information is very difficult, mostly using resources available from the internet.
- In future courses of action, we propose:
 - 1) To design a training on research methodology for Higher Education Tutors (Alonso y Palomares, 2013) on the Historical Research.
 - 2) To implement and evaluate proposed program activities.

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